

MATHEMATICAL DEVELOPMENT IN PRESCHOOL CHILDREN, INTELLECTUAL ABILITIES AS AN EDUCATIONAL MODULE

Mo'minova Gulasal Baxodirovna

Teacher of the Kokand State Pedagogical institute

Toshpo'latova Nozmexr

Student of the Kokand State Pedagogical institute

Maxmudova Xushnuza

Student of the Kokand State Pedagogical institute

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10218743>

Annotation. The introduction of STEAM education technology into the field of preschool education, training as a elective subject is carried out not only to specialists working in the preschool education system and students of higher education institutions studying in this field. Students studying in higher education institutions using STEAM education technology are changing their outlook on education. Preschoolers, educators, educators, educators, and their parents (legal representatives) may use STEAM technology based on the needs of Education. In the world educational experience, the process and state of use of STEAM – technology are analyzed.

Keywords: STEAM, creativity, training, cognitive, game method, teaching technology, activity, developing environment, STEAM educators, creative thinking, aesthetic pleasure, intellectual ability.

In preschool children, mathematical concepts are given to children, making mathematical development, intellectual abilities difficult in the educational module from simple to complex.

Initially elementary mathematical concepts: large-small, Long-Short, many-rare, wide-narrow are given and are practically performed in STEAM laboratories through didactic games. Taking into account the age characteristics of children in the development of mathematical representations, step-by-step concepts are explained theoretically and practically.

It embodies such concepts as being able to distinguish geometric figures for preschool children, developing their intellectual abilities by projecting complex edged objects, enriching contemplation through sensory education, developing a worldview, educating children in the spirit of ingenuity.

The " Robotics " Module is one of the most demanded urgent issues in the modern educational process. Today, young children are surrounded by automated systems, and from the ability to act scientifically in their components - technical progress depends on the further acceleration of production in our country and around the world. Various automatic devices occupy such a solid

place in a person's life that without them it is almost impossible to imagine modern civilization. However, the history of robotics is very long, people have learned to create different machines for almost their entire history. Of course, ancient machines could not be compared with modern ones, they had more similarities. However, they show that the ideas of creating machines, in particular, artificial imitation of a person, can be observed in the most ancient layers of human history. The word was coined by the famous Karel Chapek. He first used the term in the title of his 1920 play "Rossum universal Robots". However, he cannot be considered the author of the word "robot", which comes only from the Czech robot, which means "work". According to the writer, his brother Joseph suggested the word "robot", while Chapek himself could not decide how to name his heroes. The plot of the game Chapek seems familiar to many: at first people use their mechanical servants in various heavy jobs, then they rise up and in turn enslave people. In the modern sense, a "robot" is a mechanical device that works according to a certain program, without the help of people.

In 1941, Isaac Asimov's famous robot technique laws were formulated in the story "The Liar", designed to regulate the behavior of these machines.

1. The Robot cannot harm a person or allow this damage due to inactivity.
 2. The Robot is obliged to obey a person if it does not contradict the first law.
 3. A robot can defend itself if it does not contradict the first two laws.
- Later, Asimov himself and other authors, starting with these laws, created huge works dedicated to the relationship between people and machines.

The first robot with reliable data stored was designed by Leonardo da Vinci. It was an android that looked like an armored knight. According to Leonardo's paintings, he could move his hands and head. The question remains open as to why the famous inventor did not give his knight the ability to move his legs, that is, to walk. Perhaps he considered it a technically difficult problem (which is absolutely true). Or it was assumed that the knight should ride a horse, and the mobility of the legs is not necessary for him. It is not known whether Da Vinci was able to build his "Terminator", but he created a robotic lion, which when the King appeared tore off his chest with its claws and unveiled the coat of arms of France hidden in it. In addition, Leonardo had ideas about the interaction of mechanisms with human organs, that is, in the 15th-early 16th centuries, he expected the modern development of prostheses, which were directly controlled

by the human nervous system. During the 16th century, many devices were created in Europe, mainly using winding (clock) mechanisms. For example, in Germany, an artificial fly and an eagle are made that can fly, and in Italy, a robotic woman who plays *lutta*. Throughout the 17th century, Europeans developed and improved the first mechanical “accounting machines”. At first they can only be added and subtracted, but by the end of the century they are already able to divide and multiply. There are known stories of various humanoid machines invented and used in the United States in the 19th century:

- In 1865, the Steam man was created by designer Johnny Breynard, who was wrapped in a cart instead of a horse. It was, in fact, a steamer that looked like a person (only larger than its size). He had to “drown” all the time, and they drove him like a horse with a bridle. It was claimed that he could “walk” at 50 km / h.

- Some time later, Frank Reed tests the “electric man”, but little is known about this invention.

- In 1893, Archie Campin presented a model of an artificial soldier powered by steam, which was supposedly used in practice, that is, in battles.

In kindergarten and elementary school, the following concepts serve to study coordinates, graphs, cycles, multitasking, practical acquaintance with speed, strength, etc., mathematics, physics, programming and other areas.

Robotics training contributes to the development of logical thinking, attention, memory, imagination, creative abilities, motor skills and communication skills.

Modern robotics is divided into the following areas:

- science of automated technical systems-industry / technology,
- the household,
- aviation, military, space
- the mercury is divided into submersible water.
- Each of these areas has a basic design.

The” Robotics ” Module includes several designers to produce robots with motion capabilities. With age, the tasks solved by the child are gradually complicated, the preschool child acquires the skills of completing tasks from a simple assembly, to programming the mechanical movement control systems of the model.

In the module, machines, structures, various technical means (fixed parameters or theoretical design, relying on the sample) are created. During the work, sketches, drawings, drawings are created, calculations are carried out. The

design type is modeled. When focusing on any object or information about it, its complete or partial similarity is created. Materials at the same time, the model can be very important, the most important thing is that this model reflects the important characteristics of the object-it will be a building, Road, aircraft or ship. Based on the model, an order-miniature copy is created.

References:

1. Рузиматов, Р. Я., Махкамов, Г. М., Отажонова, С. Р., & Турсунова, Ш. А. (2017). Промышленное развитие в Коканде, причины экологических проблем (1956-1975гг.). Высшая школа, (6), 77-78.
2. Isabayeva, M. M., & Otajonova, S. R. An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal.
3. Isabayeva, M. M., & Otajonova, S. R. (2021). Pedagogical factors of preparation of future teachers of biology for professional-pedagogical activities. ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal, 11(6), 48-51.
4. Otajonova, S. (2021, July). PESTS OF FRUIT ORCHARDS IN THE TERRITORY OF KOKAND. In Конференции.
5. Otajonova, S. (2021). PESTS OF FRUIT ORCHARDS IN THE TERRITORY OF KOKAND: <https://doi.org/10.47100/conferences.v1i1.1318>. In RESEARCH SUPPORT CENTER CONFERENCES (No. 18.06).
6. Асқарова, М. А., Отажонова, С. Р., Алимова, М. Б., & Ирматова, М. Д. (2020). READING-INTELLIGENCE AS A CAPACITY-BUILDING TOOL. Scientific and Technical Journal of Namangan Institute of Engineering and Technology, 2(7), 398-402.
7. Rakhimova, G., Narimonova, Z., Otajonova, S., & Abdulxaeva, M. (2019). Stereotypy and poetics of the endemic of recit. Journal of Advanced Research in Dynamical and Control Systems, 11(7), 966-969.
8. Norquzieva, D. S., & Abdullaeva, N. R. (2019). PSYCHOLOGICAL ANALYSIS OF AGGRESSIVE BEHAVIOR IN ADOLESCENCE. Scientific and Technical Journal of Namangan Institute of Engineering and Technology, 1(6), 490-495.
9. Khamidovna, M. I., Seralievna, N. D., & Okhunovna, M. D. (2022). CONFLICT MANAGEMENT AND TYPES OF CONFLICTS AMONG MINORS. International Journal of Early Childhood Special Education, 14(7).
10. Seralievna, N. D. (2022). FORMATION OF CONSTRUCTIVE BEHAVIOR AS A FACTOR IN THE EFFECTIVENESS OF SCHOOLCHILDREN'S EDUCATION. Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal, 10(12), 1212-1216.
11. Seralievna, N. D. (2021). DYNAMICS OF CONSTRUCTIVE BEHAVIOR FORMATION IN PRIMARY SCHOOL STUDENTS. Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal, 9(10), 666-669.

12. Sheralievna, N. D. (2022). FORMATION OF CONSTRUCTIVE BEHAVIOR AS A FACTOR IN THE EFFECTIVENESS OF SCHOOLCHILDREN'S EDUCATION. *Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal*, 10(12), 1212-1216.
13. Norqo'Ziyeva, D. S. (2021). ILK O'SPIRINLARNI KASBGA YO'NALTIRISHNING AYRIM PSIXOLOGIK MASALALARI. *Scientific progress*, 1(6), 1188-1192.
14. Bakhtiyarovich, U. D. (2022). IMPROVEMENT OF THE SYSTEM OF NATIONAL STRATEGIES IN THE PROCESS OF REFORMS IN THE SPIRITUAL AND EDUCATIONAL SPHERE OF THE UPDATED UZBEKISTAN. *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCE & INTERDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH* ISSN: 2277-3630 Impact factor: 7.429, 11(05), 99-102.
15. Хамрақулов, З. Й. (2022). Ҳуқуқшунослик фанларини ўқитишда замонавий таълим технологияларидан фойдаланиш. *Pedagog*, 1(3), 314-318.
16. Хамрақулов, З. Й. (2022). Ҳуқуқшунослик фанларини ўқитишда замонавий таълим технологияларидан фойдаланиш. *Pedagog*, 1(3), 314-318.
17. Khamrakulov, Z. (2022). PROBLEMS OF INCREASING LEGAL INFORMATION AND LEGAL LITERACY OF YOUTH. *Models and methods in modern science*, 1(16), 4-7.
18. Egamberdiyeva, T. U. A., & Qurbonov, J. A. (2020). Diagnostics of formation and development of intellectual culture among students. *Scientific Bulletin of Namangan State University*, 2(4), 512-519.
19. Akmaljonovich, K. J. (2019). The necessity of developing intellectual culture of students by the subject of philosophy. *European Journal of Research and Reflection in Educational Sciences* Vol, 7(12).
20. Qurbonov, J. A. (2019). Social-pedagogical content of intellectually cultural pointh. *Scientific Bulletin of Namangan State University*, 1(5), 437-442.
21. Akmaljonovich, K. J. (2021). The Content and Essence of the Concept of "Intellectual Culture". *European Journal of Humanities and Educational Advancements*, 2(5), 15-18.
22. Akmaljonovich, K. J. (2022). Role Of Philosophy Education In Forming Intellectual Culture In Future Teachers. *Journal of Positive School Psychology*, 6(11), 1366-1371.
23. Акмалжонович, Қ. Ж. (2020). ТАЛАБАЛАР ИНТЕЛЛЕКТУАЛ МАДАНИЯТИНИ РИВОЖЛАНТИРИШДА ФАЛСАФА ФАНИНИ ЎҚИТИШНИНГ

- ПЕДАГОГИК ЖИҲАТЛАРИ. Современное образование (Узбекистан), (6 (91)), 42-49.
24. Акмалжонович, Қ. Ж. (2019). Талабалар интеллектуал маданиятини ривожлантиришнинг фалсафий-педагогик жиҳатлари. Современное образование (Узбекистан), (10 (83)), 3-9.
25. Akmaljonovich, K. J. (2022). Objective and Subjective Socio-Pedagogical Factors for the Formation of Intellectual Culture in Future Teachers. American Journal of Social and Humanitarian Research, 3(12), 148-151.
26. Юлдашева, М. М. (2017). Жамиятда ёшларнинг турли иллатлардан асрашнинг самарали йўллари. Молодой ученый, (4-2), 59-60.
27. Юлдашева, М. М., & Каршиева, Ш. В. (2017). Ёшларимизнинг маънавий-ғоявий шаклланишида интернетнинг роли. Молодой ученый, (4-2), 58-59.
28. Юлдашева, М. М. (2017). Мамлакатимизда ижтимоий-иқтисодий ва демократик ислохотларнинг амалга оширида миллий ғоя ва миллий тафаккурнинг ўрни. Молодой ученый, (4-2), 56-58.
29. Юлдашева, М. М., & Тобиров, О. К. (2016). РОЛЬ СМИ В ЖИЗНИ ОБЩЕСТВА. Ученый XXI века, 29.
30. Юлдашева, М. М., & Тобиров, О. К. (2016). СЕМЬЯ И ИДЕОЛОГИЧЕСКАЯ ДИСЦИПЛИНА ПОВЫШЕНИЯ ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТИ СИСТЕМЫ ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ. Ученый XXI века, 17.
31. Юлдашева, М. М., & Аъзамов, Б. М. (2016). Бузғунчи ва вайронкор ғоялар ва уларнинг характерли хусусиятлар. Молодой ученый, (3-1), 63-64.
32. Юлдашева, М. М., & Каршиева, Ш. В. (2016). Ёшларнинг маънавий-мафкуравий хуружларнинг объектига айланиб қолиши сабаб. Молодой ученый, (3-1), 64-65.
33. Юлдашева, М. М., & Рузиматов, У. С. (2015). РОЛЬ МОЛОДЁЖИ В ФОРМИРОВАНИИ СИСТЕМЫ ИДЕОЛОГИЧЕСКОГО ИММУНИТЕТА. Ученый XXI века, (12).
34. Urinboyev, D. (2019). Thoughts About Stratagema Of Western And Eastern Thinkers. Scientific Bulletin of Namangan State University, 1(4), 147-151.
35. Bakhtiyorovich, U. D. (2022). Features of the manifestation of strategems and the relationship between them. ASIA PACIFIC JOURNAL OF MARKETING & MANAGEMENT REVIEW ISSN: 2319-2836 Impact Factor: 7.603, 11(11), 96-100.
36. Bakhtiyarovich, U. D. (2022). IMPROVEMENT OF THE SYSTEM OF NATIONAL STRATEGIES IN THE PROCESS OF REFORMS IN THE SPIRITUAL AND EDUCATIONAL SPHERE OF THE UPDATED UZBEKISTAN. INTERNATIONAL

JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCE & INTERDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH ISSN: 2277-3630 Impact factor: 7.429, 11(05), 99-102.

37. Baratbayev, B. B. (2021). Structural Directions Of Modern Concepts Of National Development Models Of Uzbekistan And Russia. The American Journal of Political Science Law and Criminology, 3(01), 15-20.

38. Ravshanov, F., & Baratbaev, B. (2021). Structural Directions of National Development Models of Uzbekistan and Russia. INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF MULTIDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH AND ANALYSIS, 4(01), 64-67.

39. Baratbaev, B. B. (2020). STAGES OF DEVELOPMENT OF NATIONAL MODELS OF DEVELOPMENT OF UZBEKISTAN AND RUSSIA. Journal of Central Asian Social Studies, 1(02), 21-32.

40. Баратбаев, Б. (2020). METHODS OF FORMATION OF MODELS OF NATIONAL DEVELOPMENT IN UZBEKISTAN AND RUSSIA. МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫЙ ЖУРНАЛ КОНСЕНСУС, 1(4).

41. Baratbaev, B. (2020). PROCESSES OF ORGANIZING NATIONAL DEVELOPMENT IN THE CONDITIONS OF THE INDEPENDENT REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN AND THE RUSSIAN FEDERATION. East European Scientific Journal, 2(11 (63)), 10-13.

42. Баратбаев, Б. (2021). Россия тараққиёт моделини амалга тадбиқ этиш сиёсати ва унинг натижалари. Общество и инновации, 2(1/S), 194-202.

43. Баратбаев, Б. (2021). Политика реализации модели развития России и ее результаты. Общество и инновации, 2(1/S), 194-202.

44. Davronovich, M. A. (2022). HUMAN PHENOMENON IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF NEW UZBEKISTAN. ASIA PACIFIC JOURNAL OF MARKETING & MANAGEMENT REVIEW ISSN: 2319-2836 Impact Factor: 7.603, 11(11), 40-42.

45. Davronovich, M. A. (2022). PHILOSOPHY OF THE CONCEPT OF HAPPINESS IN UZBEK AND ENGLISH. ASIA PACIFIC JOURNAL OF MARKETING & MANAGEMENT REVIEW ISSN: 2319-2836 Impact Factor: 7.603, 11(11), 37-39.

46. Davronovich, M. A. (2022). PHILOSOPHICAL VIEWS OF RENE DEKART IN THE WORK "THE FIRST PHILOSOPHY". INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCE & INTERDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH ISSN: 2277-3630 Impact factor: 7.429, 11(06), 176-180.

47. Azizjon, M. (2022). COVERAGE OF ISSUES OF RAISING THE SPIRITUALITY OF A PERSON IN THE PHILOSOPHICAL VIEWS OF ABU MANSUR MOTORIDI. Yosh Tadqiqotchi Jurnali, 1(5), 422-428.

48. Davronovich, M. A., & Kholmirezayevich, M. I. (2020). THE DEVELOPMENT OF SMALL BUSINESS AND ITS SOCIO-ECONOMIC AFFECTS. MODERN VIEWS AND RESEARCH, 33.

